

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335757308>

Professional Skills and Work Ethics of Selected Faculty in a Local College

Research · September 2019

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16693.83686

CITATIONS

0

READS

89

3 authors:

John Mark R. Asio

Gordon College, Olongapo

11 PUBLICATIONS 10 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Erin Riego de Dios

Gordon College, Olongapo

7 PUBLICATIONS 8 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

April Mercy Lapuz

Gordon College, Olongapo

2 PUBLICATIONS 2 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Teacher Bullying [View project](#)

21st Century Attributes and Skills of a Teacher in the Perspective of College Students [View project](#)

PROFESSIONAL SKILLS AND WORK ETHICS OF SELECTED FACULTY IN A LOCAL COLLEGE

John Mark R. Asio, Erin E. Riego De Dios and April Mercy E. Lapuz
College of Education, Arts and Sciences
Gordon College, Olongapo City, Philippines

Abstract

Professionalism and ethicality in the institution are fundamental in running an organization. It aims to assess the professional skills and work ethics of some selected faculty of a local college in Central Luzon. A descriptive-correlational design was used, and we also used a convenience sampling technique in this study. A self-made questionnaire was made which focuses on the two major aspects of the research the professional skills with seven indicators and the work ethics with five indicators. After the survey, the data were subjected to statistical treatment using SPSS 20 and the following results were got: the respondent was a College of Education Arts and Sciences (CEAS) instructor, aged between 36 years old and above, female, single, with MA/MS units, with teaching experience of 1-5 years and a Roman Catholic by belief. For professional skills and work ethics, the respondents were *Very Good* in all the indicators. There were no significant differences in the professional skills of the respondents when grouped according to the demographic profile, however, with work ethics, there were significant findings in terms of sex and college. A relationship exists between professional skills and the work ethics of the respondents. We observed the same between work ethics, sex, and college. Based on the results of the study, recommendations were given and proposed.

Keywords: *Central Luzon, Faculty, Local College, Professional Skills, Work Ethics*

Introduction

A good set of professional skills and work ethics is a vital ingredient in working in an organization. This is most especially when you are part of the educational system. As Gines (2013) argued, that professionalization in adult education is one that is least studied especially towards professional development and performance improvement. In a higher education context, Trede (2012) identified that students are learners and in the workplace, students are pre-accredited professionals and in both contexts, they can be facilitators of peer learning.

There is also a drastic change in the educational system wherein based on the study of Rose (2012), there were factors influencing the increase in graduate student populations and this is in response to the generation of new knowledge clusters and to societal need with respect to the social and economic drivers which is a characteristic of the emerging post-industrial environments. Burke (2013) on the other hand endorsed an experiential approach to professional development allowing teachers the opportunities to improve their performance through demonstration, observation, collaboration, fieldwork, and reflection. These elements are necessary to build upon a solid foundation, especially if you are still a novice in the field.

However, in the context of perception towards their professional job, Usop, Askandar, Kadtong and Usop (2013) expressed in their study that if a teacher is contented with their job, they will develop and maintain a high degree of performance. The teaching-learning process makes more efficient and effective individuals that operate competitively in the arena of professionalism. Jackson (2015) also stated that what students experienced during placement,

broadly aligns with the best practice principles for work-integrated learning programs and problems experienced in performing certain skills during placement can be largely attributed to poor design.

Works ethics, on the other hand, is defined meticulously by people who depend on its usage on the field of the profession that it falls into the concept of what is morally good or bad. Banks (2016) argued that the concept of ethics work is an important antidote to rules-based managerialism. Although many professional organizations have adopted formal and well-established codes of ethics (e.g. the Canadian Psychological Association, American Medical Association), the academic profession has a varied response to this notion. Allana, Asad, and Sherali (2010) asserted that the influence of teachers and educators on their students immensely impacts their outcomes as well as their roles in the contemporary society especially when it comes to gender. Having an ethical notion provides a very reliable source of sound judgment and decision making of an individual. Crebert, Patrick, Cragolini, Smith, Wordfold, and Webb (2011) discussed that there is a debate over the extent to which universities can develop ethical behavior and social responsibility on students than any other graduate skills or attributes. Further, Calvano and Wang (2015) indicated that men are responsive to business ethics education than women. As Saleh (2018) also introduced that whatever the size effect and duration, ethics of the profession appear obvious and clear at all levels of the institutions and its various kinds. Furthermore, the institution should train its students in their ethical behaviors and code of ethics (Mohamad, Rahman, Usman & Tawil, 2015; Shobana & Kanakarathinam, 2017; Rodzalan & Saat, 2016).

The objective of this study is to gauge the professional skills and work ethics of selected faculty of a local college in Central Luzon. It also aims to identify if there is a relationship between professional skills and work ethics. The result of the study would be beneficial to the school administration and the institution in giving the necessary professional development program for the faculty of the institution to enrich and provide better output and performance.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive correlational technique in analyzing the professional skills and work ethics of the faculty and its possible relationship to each other. The respondents for this study include 45 full-time faculty members of a Local College located in Central Luzon. They were currently teaching during the Summer Class of the academic year of 2017-2018. The researcher created a self-made questionnaire which undergone reliability and validity tests prior to actual administration of the survey.

All the data and information were tallied, classified and analyzed with the help of Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The weighted values assigned to the professional skills and work ethics were patterned after the Likert scale.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 represents the demographic profile of the respondents in the study. It can be seen that the College of Education, Arts and Sciences dominated other departments of the institution since they have the number of respondents. Also, the age of the respondents falls under the bracket of 36 years old and above. There were slightly more females than males, and most of the respondents were also single. In terms of educational attainment, most of them have already earned their bachelor's degree and possess master's degree units. More respondents fall under the beginning years (1-5 years of service) of work and the majority are

Roman Catholic in faith. It can then be deduced that the above information generally describes a typical faculty working in a department of an institution of learning.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
College		
CEAS	27	60
CBA	9	20
CAHS	4	9
CCS	5	11
Total	45	100
Age		
21-25 years old	12	27
26-30 years old	10	22
31-35 years old	8	18
36 years old above	15	33
Total	45	100
Sex		
Male	21	47
Female	24	53
Total	45	100
Civil Status		
Single	27	60
Married	18	40
Total	45	100
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Graduate	5	11
MA/ MS Units	26	58
MA/ MS Graduate	9	20
PhD Unit	5	11
Total	45	100
Length of Service		
1-5 years	20	44
6-10 years	7	16
11-15 years	8	18
16 years above	10	22
Total	45	100
Religion		
Roman Catholic	38	87
Born Again	2	3
Others	5	10
Total	45	100

Professional Skills of the Respondent

Table 2 represents the mean of the professional skills of the respondents in the study. As seen, we divide it into seven (7) major indicators and each contains four (4) items. For the first indicator, item number three got the highest mean score. For the second indicator, item number one got the highest means score. For the third indicator, item number three got the highest mean score. For the fourth indicator, item number one got the highest mean score. For the fifth indicator, item number three got the highest mean score. For the sixth indicator, item number two got the highest mean score and for the seventh indicator, item number four got the highest mean score. The overall mean got a descriptive interpretation of very good, which can be observed throughout the table. It is, therefore, safe to say that the respondents are very competent and reliable in terms of professionalism in their workplace.

Table 2. Professional Skills of the Respondents

Variables	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Manage Learning Environment		
1. Obtain required equipment, systems, tools, supplies and materials.	3.98	Very Good
2. Set up and maintain instructional systems, equipment and/or tools.	4.07	Very Good
3. Supervise learning environment.	4.31	Very Good
4. Evaluate and monitor the safety of the instructional areas and practices.	4.09	Very Good
Develop Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula		
1. Identify, evaluate and modify current outcomes.	4.04	Very Good
2. Create, evaluate and modify curriculum and assessment.	4.00	Very Good
3. Implement curriculum, outcomes and assessment.	3.93	Very Good
4. Integrate curriculum with other faculty in the department and in other area/ institution.	4.00	Very Good
Provide Student Instruction		
1. Prepare and/or gather current instructional materials and equipment.	4.33	Very Good
2. Provide individual and group instruction.	4.33	Very Good
3. Initiate, develop and implement student assessment.	4.40	Very Good
4. Modify instructional material and methods based on student and industry assessment and feedback.	4.29	Very Good
Provide Support and Guidance to Students		
1. Respond to student needs and provide information or referrals.	4.44	Very Good
2. Assist students with job placement.	3.87	Very Good
3. Provide academic and career advising.	4.24	Very Good
4. Serve as student activity advisors as applicable.	4.22	Very Good
Create and Maintain a Professional Environment		
1. Collaborate with college staff, faculty and students.	4.33	Very Good
2. Serve on department and college committees.	4.16	Very Good
3. Maintain current knowledge of the field.	4.53	Excellent
4. Develop a professional development plan.	4.27	Very Good
Learn and Adapt New Technologies		
1. Obtain and maintain certification on program-specific technology.	4.11	Very Good
2. Maintain current knowledge of technology in the field.	4.24	Very Good
3. Identify, evaluate and implement emerging technologies according to industry needs.	4.16	Very Good
4. Identify and evaluate and implement new instructional technologies.	4.11	Very Good
Participation for Professional Growth and Development		
1. Join professional organizations, groups, or association within or outside the institution.	4.31	Very Good
2. Participate to seminars, assemblies, conventions, colloquium, etc.	4.33	Very Good
3. Initiate and publish a research locally, nationally or internationally.	3.78	Very Good
4. Enroll for higher degrees (MA/PhD), certification programs and the like.	4.47	Very Good
Overall Mean	4.19	Very Good

*Likert Scale: 1.00-1.49=Needs Improvement; 1.50-2.49=Poor; 2.50-3.49=Good; 3.50-4.49=Very Good; 4.50-5.00=Excellent

The result somehow corresponds to the study by Tanguihan in 2016, where she described the teacher competencies of some selected higher education institutions of Surigao City and found out that all the instructors were all competent in this area.

Work Ethics of the Respondents

Table 3 represents the mean scores of the respondents in terms of work ethics. It can be observed that it is composed of five (5) major indicators with four (4) items each. For the first indicator, item number four got the highest mean score. For the second indicator, it is the first item that got the highest means score, the same result also is seen for the third indicator. However, the fourth indicator got two items tied for the highest mean scores (item number one and four) and for the fifth indicator it is item number one that got the highest mean score. Overall, the mean of work ethics is generally labeled as very good based on the responses of the respondents. It can then be deduced that in terms of working ethics among the respondents, they are confident in giving a high response.

Table 3. Work Ethics of the Respondents

Variables	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Knowledge and Skills in their Discipline		
1. Has comprehensive skills relating to their discipline	4.38	Very Good
2. Has an interdisciplinary perspective	4.31	Very Good
3. Has the capacity to find, evaluate and use information	4.38	Very Good
4. Ability to apply discipline/professional skills and knowledge in the workplace	4.39	Very Good
Effective Communicators and Team Members		
1. Has the capacity to communicate effectively with others orally	4.36	Very Good
2. Has the capacity to communicate effectively with others in writing	4.33	Very Good
3. Has the capacity to communicate effectively with others using ICTs, visuals, multimedia, musicals and other forms appropriate to their discipline	4.29	Very Good
4. Has capacity to interact and collaborate with others effectively, including in teams, in the workplace, and in culturally or linguistically diverse context	4.24	Very Good
Innovative and Creative, with Critical Judgment		
1. Has ability to use knowledge and skills to devise solutions to unfamiliar problems	4.24	Very Good
2. Has ability to analyze and critically evaluate arguments and evidence appropriate to their discipline	4.22	Very Good
3. Has knowledge to research methodologies in their disciplines and capacity to evaluate findings	4.16	Very Good
4. Has ability to generate ideas/products/art works/methods/approaches/perspectives as appropriate to discipline	4.16	Very Good
Socially Responsible and Engaged in their Communities		
1. Has ethical awareness (personal and professional) and academic integrity	4.56	Excellent
2. Capacity to apply disciplinary knowledge to solving real life problems in relevant communities	4.51	Excellent
3. Has understanding of social and civic responsibilities, human rights and sustainability	4.53	Excellent
4. Has understanding the value of further learning and professional development	4.56	Excellent
Competent in Culturally Diverse Environment		
1. Has awareness of and respect for the values of different people	4.64	Excellent
2. Has awareness and respect for the knowledge of the indigenous people	4.58	Excellent
3. Has respect, awareness, knowledge and skills to interact effectively in linguistically or culturally diverse context	4.49	Very Good
4. Has a global and international perspective on their disciplines	4.40	Very Good
Overall Mean	4.39	Very Good

*Likert Scale: 1.00-1.49=Needs Improvement; 1.50-2.49=Poor; 2.50-3.49=Good; 3.50-4.49=Very Good; 4.50-5.00=Excellent

Concerning the findings, Shobana & Kanakarathinam (2017) argued that teachers with a high level of moral proficiency have a deep commitment to helping students gain and perform which provides the students to have continuous growth in their lives. Saleh (2018) also concluded that Educational institutions at all levels have the major duty of spreading the culture of work ethics among the personnel and the students by converging on the principle of manners before education.

Significant Differences in the Professional Skills and Works Ethics when Grouped According to Profile Variables

Table 4 represents the independent-samples t-test to compare the professional skills and work ethics awareness of the respondents. There was a significant difference in the scores of male (M=4.24, SD=0.38) and female (M=4.53, SD=0.48), $t(43) = -2.223, p=0.032$. The result suggests that sex does affect the awareness of the respondents regarding work ethics. On the other hand, there was no significant difference in the scores of the single (M=4.39, SD=0.33) and married (M=4.38, SD=0.61) respondents, $t(43) = 0.059, p=0.953$. The result then suggests that civil status does not affect the awareness of respondents in terms of work ethics. Furthermore, there were also no significant differences in the scores of the respondents when grouped according to sex and civil status. Since the following scores for males (M=4.05, SD=0.50) and female (M=4.32, SD=0.46), $t(43) = -1.888, p=0.066$; and for single (M=4.21, SD=0.43) and married (M=4.16, SD=0.58), $t(43) = 0.293, p=0.771$ were obtained, the results then recommend that either sex or civil status can affect the professional skills awareness of respondents.

Table 4. T test for Significant Differences for Professional Skills and Work Ethics when Grouped according to Sex and Civil Status

	Professional Skills		Work Ethics	
	M	SD	M	SD
Male (n=21)	4.05	0.50	4.24	0.38*
Female (n=24)	4.32	0.46	4.53	0.48*
Single (n=27)	4.21	0.43	4.39	0.33
Married (n=18)	4.16	0.58	4.38	0.61

*df = 43; *p < .05*

In contrast, Algadheeb (2015) found out that there was a significant difference in the professional awareness variable in favor of female respondents in her study in a university in Saudi Arabia.

A similar finding however was found by Wang and Calvano (2015) wherein they indicated that women are more ethical than men who were also seconded by Rodzalan and Saat (2016) where female students appear to have a higher level of ethics than the male counterpart.

Table 5 presents the one-way between subjects ANOVA was conducted to compare the effects of college/ department, age, educational attainment, years of service and religion to professional skills awareness. As seen from the table, there was no significant effect of college, age, educational attainment, years of service and religion to professional skills awareness at the $p > .05$ level since the following results were obtained $F(3, 41) = 0.161, p = .380$; $F(3, 41) = 1.191, p=0.325$; $F(3, 41)=0.170, p=0.916$; $F(3, 41) = 2.078, p=0.118$; $F(3, 41)=0.857, p=0.432$, respectively. In comparison to the study of Tanguihan (2016), she found a significant difference in the level of competencies among teachers.

Table 5. ANOVA for Professional Skills of Respondents

		SS	dF	MS	F value
College	Between Groups	0.758	3	.112	1.051
	Within	9.857	41	.700	
	Total	10.615	44		
Age	Between Groups	0.851	3	.284	1.191
	Within	9.764	41	.238	
	Total	10.615	44		
Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.130	3	.043	0.170
	Within	10.485	41	.256	
	Total	10.615	44		
Years of Service	Between Groups	1.401	3	.467	2.078
	Within	9.214	41	.225	
	Total	10.615	44		
Religion	Between Groups	0.416	3	.208	0.857
	Within	10.199	41	.243	
	Total	10.615	44		

$p > 0.05$

Table 6 presents the one-way between-subjects ANOVA was conducted to compare the effects of college/department, age, educational attainment, years of service and religion to work ethics awareness. It can be gleaned that college yielded a significant effect on work ethics awareness of the respondents since $F(3, 41) = 3.351$, $p = 0.028$. However, the rest of the variables like age, educational attainment, years of service and religion do not have a significant effect on the work ethics awareness of the respondents, since the following results were obtained, $F(3,41) = 0.411$, $p=0.746$; $F(3,41) = 1.109$, $p=0.356$; $F(3,41) = 2.804$, $p=0.052$; $F(2,42) = 0.661$, $p = 0.522$, respectively.

Table 6. ANOVA for Work Ethics Awareness

		SS	dF	MS	F value
College	Between Groups	1.817	3	.606	3.351*
	Within	7.410	41	.181	
	Total	9.226	44		
Age	Between Groups	0.269	3	.090	0.411
	Within	8.957	41	.218	
	Total	9.226	44		
Educational Background	Between Groups	0.693	3	.231	1.109
	Within	8.534	41	.208	
	Total	9.226	44		
Years of Service	Between Groups	1.571	3	.524	2.804
	Within	7.656	41	.187	
	Total	9.226	44		
Religion	Between Groups	0.282	2	.141	0.661
	Within	8.945	42	.213	
	Total	9.226	44		

* $p < 0.05$

In consonance with the result is the study of Rodzalan and Saat (2016) that in terms of departments, they also found a significant result. However, van der Walt, Jonck, and Sobayeni (2016) showed a statistical difference in some facets of work ethics when grouped according to three generational cohorts.

Correlation between Profile Variables, Professional Skills and Work Ethics

Table 7 constitutes the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient to assess the relationships between the profile variables, professional skills and work ethics awareness of the respondents. There was a negative correlation between college and work ethics awareness, $r = -.358$, $n = 45$, $p = .016$. There was also a positive correlation between sex and work ethics awareness, $r = .321$, $n = 45$, $p = .032$. These could only mean that some profile variables (e.g. college and sex) are related to work ethics awareness to some extent.

Table 7. Correlation Matrix between Profile Variables, Professional Skills and Work Ethics

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
College	1								
Sex	-.133	1							
Age	.244	.116	1						
Civil Status	.186	.400**	.400**	1					
Educ. Background	.162	.139	.385**	.078	1				
Years of Service	.273	.027	.614**	.291	.214	1			
Religion	-.018	-.165	-.027	-.056	-.201	.024	1		
Professional Skills	-.202	.277	.190	-.045	-.070	.030	-.165	1	
Work Ethics	-.358*	.321*	.163	-.009	-.017	.051	-.148	.795**	1

* $p > 0.05$; ** $p > 0.01$

There was also a strong, positive correlation between professional skills and work ethics awareness since $r = .795$, $n = 45$, $p = .000$. This could only mean that an increase in professional skills awareness can contribute to an increase in work ethics awareness also.

In contrast to the results, Tanguihan (2016) showed that age and length of teaching experience were significantly related to the competencies of teachers. A study also by Murtaza, Abbas, Raja, Roque, Khalid and Mushtaq (2016) showed that Islamic work ethics has a positive effect on organizational citizenship behaviors and knowledge-sharing behaviors.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: 1) the respondent of the study is a College of Education Arts and Sciences (CEAS) instructor, aged between 36 years old and above, female, single, with MA/MS units, with teaching experience of 1-5 years and a Roman Catholic by belief. 2) In terms of professional skills, the respondents were generally *Very Good* when it comes to Management of Learning Environment, Development of Outcomes, Assessment and Curricula, Provision of Student Instruction, Provision of Support and Guidance to Students, Creation and Maintenance of a Professional Environment, Learning and Adapting to New Technologies and Participation to Professional Growth and Development. 3) In terms of a work ethics of the respondents, they were also *Very Good* in general, however, the fourth indicator (Socially Responsible and Engaged in their Communities) got an *Excellent* score in all four (4) items and the fifth (Competent in Culturally Diverse and International Environment) indicator has two (2) items with *Excellent* score. The rest of the indicators namely Knowledgeable and Skilled in their Discipline, Effective Communicators and Team Member, Innovative and Creative, with Critical Judgment, got a response of *Very Good* in all of their items. 4) There were no significant differences in the professional skills of the respondents when grouped according to the demographic profile. However, in the case of work ethics, there exist significant findings in terms of sex and college. 5) It was also revealed that a strong positive relationship exists between the professional skills and work ethics of the respondents. At the same time, a

weak positive relationship can also be observed between work ethics and sex and a weak negative relationship between work ethics and college.

On the basis of the aforementioned conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby presented: 1) Rigorous training of the staff should be kept at a pace in the ever-changing world of professionalism. 2) Occasional seminars, workshops, updates, and conventions should be prepared by the academic council of the institution, both inside and outside of the school. 3) Mandated membership of each faculty to an accredited organization in their field of specialization. 4) The merit system of the institution should be reviewed regularly and the faculty should be well informed with it. 5) Research-based academic performance evaluation should be integrated into the merit system. 6) Mandated participation of faculty to research-based seminars, symposia, and conventions. 7) Follow up research on the same area but with a more in-depth analysis.

References

- 1) Algadheeb, N.A. (2015). Professional/ Career orientation, awareness, and their relationship to locus of control. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning*, 12 (1), 13-38.
- 2) Ali, K.K. (2018). Awareness of ethics and integrity at a Malaysian government district office. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 53, 02007.
- 3) Allana, A., Asad, N., & Sherali, Y. (2010). Gender in academic settings: Role of teachers. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 1 (4), 343-348.
- 4) Banks, S. (2016). Everyday ethics in professional life: social work as ethics work. *Ethics and Social Welfare*, 10 (1), 32-52.
- 5) Burke, B. (2013). Experiential professional development: A model for meaningful and long lasting change in classrooms. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 36 (3), 247-263.
- 6) Crebert, G., Patrick, C.J., Cragolini, V., Smith, C., Worsfold, K., & Webb, F. (2011). Ethical behaviour and social responsibility toolkit. Retrieved from <http://www.mcs.gov.kh/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Ethical-behaviour.pdf>
- 7) Gines, A., (2013). Professionalization of adult educators: The Philippine experience. *American International Journal of Social Science*, 2 (8), 152-158.
- 8) Jackson, D. (2015). Employability skill development in work-integrated learning: barriers and best practices. *Studies in Higher Education*, 40 (2), 350-367.
- 9) Mohamad, N., Abdul Rahman, H., Usman, I.M., & Tawil, N.M. (2015). Ethics education and training for construction professional in Malaysia. *Asian Social Science*, 11 (4), 55-64.
- 10) Murtaza, G., Abbas, M., Raja, U., Roques, O., Khalid, A., & Mushtaq, R. (2016). Impact of Islamic work ethics on organizational citizenship behaviors and knowledge-sharing behaviors. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 133 (2), 325-333.
- 11) Rodzalan, S.A., & Saat, M.M. (2016). Ethics of undergraduate students: A study in Malaysian public universities. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6 (9), 672-678.
- 12) Rose, M. (2012). Graduate student professional development: A survey with recommendations. Retrieved from <http://www.cags.ca/documents/publications/working/Report%20on%20Graduate%20Student%20Professional%20Development%20%20%20A%20survey%20with%20recommendations%20FINAL%20Eng.OCT%202012.pdf>
- 13) Saleh, A. (2018). The role of educational institutes in promoting work ethics. *International Humanities Studies*, 5 (1), 33-48.

- 14) Shobana, S., & Kanakarathinam, R. (2017). Awareness and need of ethics and values in education for students: A study among college teachers in Pollachi region. *International Journal of Current Research Review*, 9 (9), 26-31.
- 15) Tanguihan, L.G. (2016) Teaching competencies of college instructors in the selected higher education institutions of Surigao City. *Proceedings Journal of Education, Psychology and Social Science Research*. 3(1), 92-98.
- 16) Trede, F., (2012). Role of work-integrated learning in developing professionalism and professional identity. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 13 (3), 159-167.
- 17) Usop, A.M., Askandar, D.K., Langguyuan_Kadtong, M., Usop, D.A.S.O., (2013). Work performance and job satisfaction among teachers. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3 (5), 245-252.
- 18) Van der Walt, F., Jonck, P., & Sobayeni, N.C. (2016). Work ethics of different generational cohorts in South Africa. *African Journal of Business Ethics*, 10 (1), 52-66.
- 19) Wang, L.C., & Calvano, L. (2015). Is business ethics education effective? An analysis of gender, personal ethical perspectives and moral judgment. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 126 (4) 591-602.